

CROWDSOURCING IN LAST MILE DELIVERY: A BIBLIOMETRIC REVIEW AND RESEARCH AGENDA

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ABSTRACT

Last mile delivery faces numerous economic, social, and environmental challenges. As a result, crowdsourcing has become a widely recognised solution to address these challenges. Current studies on this topic are fragmented, investigating diverse aspects of crowdsourcing in different contexts, and giving divergent results. Thus, an in-depth review is necessary to identify the underlying themes and future research agendas. A bibliometric analysis was performed on 217 publications exported from the Scopus database for the period 2000 to 2025. Results revealed four key themes from crowdsourcing in last mile delivery research: optimisation, sustainability, policy integration, and user acceptance. Despite their importance, user acceptance, and technological innovations themes remain underexplored in current research. Future research should prioritise investigating the integration of emerging technologies to enhance user trust, transparency, and willingness to participate in crowdsourcing. This review provides a structured framework to guide the development of user-centered, efficient, sustainable, and policy-aligned crowdsourced last mile delivery systems.

Keywords: crowdsourcing, last mile, bibliometric, review

INTRODUCTION

The rise of electronic commerce (e-commerce), urban population growth, and increasing customer expectations have resulted in unprecedented pressure on logistics systems, particularly the last mile. Last mile delivery (LMD) is the last transportation leg of goods delivery from a transportation hub (e.g., order fulfilment centre or store) to an end customer (e.g., customer's home or collection point) (Sorooshian *et al.*, 2022; Mogire, Kilbourn & Luke, 2023; Wang & Alidaee, 2023). LMD faces numerous economic, social, and environmental challenges (Alharbi, Cantarelli & Brint, 2022). It is one of the most expensive and challenging aspects when delivering online orders (Wang & Alidaee, 2023). The increasing volumes of parcels and short order notices cause tight deadlines and considerable time pressures, which cause delivery delays (Boysen, Fedtke & Schwerdfeger, 2021). The increasing volume of online orders adds more pressure on LMD, affecting road congestion, air, and noise pollution (Mogire, 2022; Mogire, Kilbourn & Luke, 2022; Puram *et al.*, 2022).

Among other options, such as parcel lockers, drones, cargo bikes, and electric vehicles, crowdsourcing is increasingly being explored as a solution to these last mile delivery challenges. According to the Collins Dictionary, crowdsourcing refers to the practice of getting ideas or help with a project from a large number of people, usually through the Internet. In the last mile delivery context, crowdsourcing involves temporary hiring of individuals by a company to deliver products, with appropriate compensation (Seghezzi *et al.*, 2021; Pamucar *et al.*, 2024). It is an innovative delivery option that relies on individuals who frequently travel for various reasons, to deliver parcels during their usual trips for payment (Bajec, Pivtorak, & Svadlenka, 2025). This implies that many people are used to performing delivery services as a secondary activity.

For customers, crowdsourced delivery has the potential to offer faster, and more affordable deliveries while enhancing service levels (Seghezzi *et al.*, 2021; Ghaderi *et al.*, 2022; Pamucar *et al.*, 2024). Reducing the number of dedicated trips from e-commerce businesses helps to lower carbon emissions and transportation costs (Ghaderi *et al.*, 2022; Pamucar *et al.*, 2024). Crowdsourcing also provides flexible working opportunities to society (Seghezzi *et al.*, 2021). Crowdsourced delivery can reduce traffic congestion and delivery time, thus contributing to sustainability (Mogire, Kilbourn & Luke, 2025b). The increasing customer demand for cost-effective last mile delivery options has resulted in the development of green innovations (such as crowdsourcing) in last mile delivery (Mogire, 2026).

PROBLEM STATEMENT AND RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Despite their potential benefits, crowdsourcing is hindered by numerous challenges, such as trust between actors, regulation issues, and supply and demand management for the service (Pamucar *et al.*, 2024). Regional studies show differing adoption factors, for instance, in China, perceived value and trust enhance continued use of crowdsourcing (Liu *et al.*, 2024), while perceived risk negatively affects its use (Liu *et al.*, 2024). In Saudi Arabia, the implementation of crowdsourcing faces legislative issues, driver availability, trust concerns, and cultural issues (Alharbi *et al.*, 2022). In South Africa, mobile-based delivery systems face legal, security, and connectivity obstacles (Okoche *et al.*, 2024). In Turkey, detailed identification and security checks were recommended among the solutions to resolve safety, security, and trust issues in crowdsourced delivery (Göçer, İzcan, & Vural, 2025). In addition, customer satisfaction is essential to the widespread use of crowdsourcing (Göçer *et al.*, 2025). In some emerging e-commerce markets, such as Kenya, crowdsourced delivery is valued by very few online customers (Mogire, 2022; Mogire, Kilbourn & Luke, 2024a). The authors recommended future research to explore the use of crowdsourcing to better understand the concept of last mile delivery.

While existing studies on crowdsourcing in last mile delivery have addressed the benefits, challenges, and feasibility, the findings are fragmented and show regional differences, limiting a holistic understanding of the topic. A keyword search in the Scopus database (Article title: ("crowdsourcing*") AND ("last mile" OR "last-mile") AND ("bibliometric")) failed to identify a study directly aligned with the focus of this review. Given the growth in research on this area over the past decade and the lack of an integrative review, a bibliometric review is necessary to map the knowledge structure, identify influential research, and synthesise existing literature to identify research gaps and inform future research. This is meant to guide policy development to encourage the broader adoption of crowdsourcing in last mile delivery. The specific objectives of this review are:

- i. To identify the themes that have been used in crowdsourcing in last mile delivery research.
- ii. To propose future research agendas on crowdsourcing in last mile delivery.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Crowdsourcing, as proposed by Howe (2006), relates to outsourcing a company's value-creation activities to an undefined network of people. The undefined network of people referred to as 'common' people is available to bring parcels from a point of collection (such as a store or warehouse) to a point of delivery. The network of people, usually natural persons, is hired by a company for delivery, with appropriate compensation (Pamucar *et al.*, 2024; Bajec *et al.*, 2025). In addition, they often deliver parcels as a secondary activity as they travel (Pamucar *et al.*, 2024;

Bajec *et al.*, 2025). This may involve the crowd travelling in cars, vans, bicycles, scooters, public transport, or even walking (Gläser, Jahnke & Strassheim, 2023). Likewise, Pamucar *et al.* (2024) assert that it includes private cars, public buses, public trains, taxi drivers, and taxi passengers. However, Seghezzi *et al.* (2021) indicate that the crowd may involve: the use of friends and acquaintances to deliver parcels for free, or people on social platforms delivering to members of their community, or a 'hybrid' that combines e-commerce vehicles with a group of occasional riders that deliver parcels in small quantities along their route at a fee.

A systematic review on the dynamics of crowdsourcing in last mile distribution within mobility found factors such as consumer satisfaction, operational and technological efficiency, environmental impact and sustainability, and economic profitability influence the success of crowdsourcing (García-Herrera, Serrano-Hernandez, & Faulin, 2025). A systematic review on sustainability benefits and risks of crowdsourcing emphasised the need for sustainable practices encompassing the economic, environmental and social dimensions (Göçer *et al.*, 2025). A systematic review by Gläser, Jahnke, and Strassheim (2023) on opportunities and challenges of crowdsourcing on the last mile service providers found opportunities for using CLD to lower operating costs, reduce emissions, improve delivery service quality, and serve new customers. However, CLD faces challenges such as a lack of laws and regulations, privacy and trust issues, and a lack of appropriate compensation schemes to attract the crowd (Gläser *et al.*, 2023). A review of platforms and academic literature on crowdsourced delivery found that most studies overlook important operational decisions like driver scheduling, routing, and compensation (Alnaggar, Gzara & Bookbinder, 2021). However, the review was limited to platforms of North American companies and systems.

A review of operational challenges and opportunities of crowdsourcing in last mile delivery identified unresolved issues concerning courier's working conditions and pricing models (Pourrahmani & Jaller, 2021). The review only explores operational challenges and opportunities in 98 studies. A systematic review on crowdsourcing for sustainability emphasises the need to understand trust mechanisms, user behaviour, and environmental implications of crowdsourcing systems to enhance sustainability in urban logistics (Mohri *et al.*, 2023). A bibliometric review on green innovations in last mile delivery for e-commerce found that crowdsourcing co-occurs with keywords like sustainability and emerging topics like service quality and efficiency (Mogire, Kilbourn & Luke, 2024b). A bibliometric analysis of sharing economy logistics and crowdsourcing emphasises that sharing mobility for last mile delivery is a source of performance for generating

innovative solutions to environmental impacts (Saglietto, 2021). However, the review was limited to 85 articles between 2007 and 2019.

From the preceding discussion, there are inconsistencies in the terminology used on the topic. While some studies use crowdsourcing, others have used 'crowd shipping' or 'crowd logistics'. In addition, some studies have a narrow focus, such as operational challenges and sustainability dimension in last mile delivery, with a small number of articles. The majority of the reviews are systematic literature reviews with limitations on relationships among themes, authors, and keywords.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A bibliometric analysis was conducted to map knowledge, highlight key studies, and identify gaps to guide future research on the topic. Bibliometric analysis utilises quantitative methods to explore large volumes of scientific data to shed light on emerging areas in a field (Donthu *et al.*, 2021). The bibliometric analysis techniques include performance analysis descriptives (e.g., authors, journals, institutions, and countries), and science mapping used to visualise relationships on the topic (e.g., citation analysis, co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, co-word analysis, and co-authorship analysis) (Donthu *et al.*, 2021; Saglietto, 2021).

The required data was extracted from the Scopus database on 15 April 2025 using the following keywords: (Article title, Abstract, Keywords (“crowdsourc*” OR “crowd sourc*” OR “crowd-sourc*” OR “crowdlogistics” OR “crowd logistics” OR “crowd-logistics” OR “crowdshipping” OR “crowd shipping” OR “crowd-shipping” OR “crowddelivery” OR “crowd delivery” OR “crowd-delivery” OR “peer-to-peer delivery” OR “p2p delivery” OR “gig delivery” OR “decentralised delivery” OR “peer assisted delivery”) AND (“last mile” OR “last-mile”) resulting to 240 publications. This was limited to articles, review papers, conference papers, and book chapters published in English from 2000 to 2025. The Scopus database was used because it is a trusted source of bibliometric data (Baas, Schotten, Plume, Côté & Karimi, 2020). The 240 publications were examined manually. Those that lacked topics, titles, and were irrelevant were deleted, resulting in 217 publications. The irrelevant articles relate to crowdsourcing in non-logistics sectors such as telecommunication and energy/ electricity networks. These were downloaded as CSV Excel file for bibliometric analysis using the Bibliometrix package version 4.3.0 (specifically the Biblioshiny app version 4.3.0).

TABLE 1 summarises the main information about the publications and results presented in the next section. Research on the topic has grown since 2013, with a high average growth rate of 27.81%. Journal articles account for the majority of publications (66.4%), whereas review papers represent the least share (5, 2.3%).

TABLE 1
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT THE PUBLICATIONS ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Description	Results
Timespan	2013:2025
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	132
Documents	217
Annual Growth Rate %	27.81
Document Average Age	3.26
Average citations per document	22.29
References	9053
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	1152
Author's Keywords (DE)	574
AUTHORS	
Authors	553
Authors of single-authored docs	10
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	10
Co-Authors per Doc	3.48
International co-authorships %	31.34
DOCUMENT TYPES	
Article	144
Book chapter	7
Conference paper	61
Review	5

RESULTS

This section presents results: performance analysis and science mapping on the topic.

Performance analysis

The initial research period from 2013 to 2015 recorded minimal research, with below one publication per year (Figure 1). Crowdsourcing was a relatively new concept during this stage, as e-commerce was still new. A slight growth in research started in 2016 with six publications and ended in 2017. Most researchers were attracted to e-commerce research during this period as

more growth was recorded in the sector. A steady increase in research output started in 2019, with 15 publications until 2022, before peaking in 2024 with 43 publications. There was widespread adoption of crowdsourcing driven by technological advancements, growth in e-commerce, and growing urban and sustainability challenges. The post-2024 can be attributed to more AI-driven logistics, smart urban mobility planning, the regulatory focus of the gig economy, and urban delivery challenges.

FIGURE 1
NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Top-cited journals

TABLE 2 shows that *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* is the most productive journal on the topic with 13 publications, an h-index of 8, a g-index of 13, and 756 total citations counted from 2016. The journal mainly focuses on optimising logistics systems. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* is an emerging journal with four publications, m-index of 0.8, and 77 total citations counted from 2021. The journal focuses on policy analysis, planning, and the management of transportation systems. Thus, most existing studies focus on optimising logistics systems, with policy analysis emerging as a growing theme on the topic.

The journals can be classified into four themes based on their scope: the logistics and supply chain optimisation theme comprises journals like the *Journal of Business Logistics*, *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, *Computers and Operations Research*, and *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*. The sustainability and smart transportation systems theme includes journals like *Sustainability Journal*, *Transportation Science*, and *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*. The transportation policy and planning theme covers journals like *Transportation Research Procedia*, and *Transportation*

Research Part A: Policy and Practice. The last theme, user behaviour and social aspects, includes the *Travel Behaviour and Society Journals*. This shows that most existing studies focus on logistics and supply chain optimisation, while few focus on user behaviour and social aspects.

TABLE 2
TOP 10 MOST CITED JOURNALS ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Rank	Journal	h-index	g-index	m-index	TC	NP	PY-start
1	Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review	8	13	0.8	756	13	2016
2	Sustainability (Switzerland)	6	9	0.75	270	9	2018
3	Transportation Research Procedia	5	10	0.625	240	10	2018
4	Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice	4	4	0.8	77	4	2021
5	Transportation Research Part B: Methodological	4	5	0.5	119	5	2018
6	Transportation Science	4	4	0.571	395	4	2019
7	Travel Behaviour and Society	4	4	0.571	141	4	2019
8	Computers and Operations Research	3	4	0.75	46	4	2022
9	International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications	3	4	0.6	110	4	2021
10	Journal of Business Logistics	3	3	0.375	230	3	2018

Top-cited authors

TABLE 3 shows that *Pedroso J.* is the most productive author with seven publications, an h-index of 6, a g-index of 7, and 178 total citations calculated from 2018. The author focuses on optimising crowdsourcing systems by modeling uncertainty and using advanced algorithms to improve last mile delivery efficiency. However, it was noted that even though *Gatta V.* and *Marcucci E.* co-authored four publications, they have 418 total citations, an h-index of 4, and a g-index of 4 calculated from 2018. Most of their studies evaluate the environmental, economic, and operational impacts of public transport-based crowdsourcing for last mile deliveries. *Liu J.* is a veteran author who started publishing on the topic in 2016. *Fessler A.* is the most productive emerging author with five publications, an m-index of 5, and 65 total citations calculated from 2022. *Fessler A.* focuses on public transport-based crowdsourcing as a sustainable solution to last mile delivery challenges

TABLE 3
TOP 10 MOST CITED AUTHORS ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Rank	Element	h-index	g-index	m-index	TC	NP	PY_start
1	Pedroso J.	6	7	0.75	178	7	2018
2	Viana A.	5	6	0.625	168	6	2018
3	Fessler A.	4	5	1	65	5	2022
4	Gatta V.	4	4	0.5	418	4	2018
5	Haustein S.	4	4	1	65	4	2022
6	Liu J.	4	4	0.4	48	4	2016
7	Marcucci E.	4	4	0.5	418	4	2018
8	Mizouni R.	4	7	1	49	8	2022
9	Otrok H.	4	7	1	49	8	2022
10	Singh S.	4	7	1	49	8	2022

Word cloud

The word cloud highlights three key research themes on the topic. The sustainability theme includes keywords like *sustainability, sustainable development, economic and social effects, traffic congestion, urban transportation, and public transport* (

FIGURE 2). The optimisation theme covers keywords like *vehicle routing, optimisation, efficiency, economics, cost-effectiveness, routings, combinational optimisation, sensitivity analysis, and fleet operations*. The technological innovation theme includes keywords like *heuristic algorithms, intelligent systems, algorithm, dynamic programming, and blockchain*. Regarding frequency, larger words like *logistics, fleet operations, and vehicle routing* appear at the centre of the word cloud, an indicator that these are the most frequent concepts on the topic. Keywords like *intelligent systems, blockchain, algorithm, and optimisation* are located at the edges of the word cloud, an indicator that they are less frequent concepts representing emerging or specialised topics.

FIGURE 2
WORD CLOUD ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Top-cited countries

TABLE 4 shows that China is the most productive country in crowdsourcing research for last mile delivery, followed by China. While most studies in the USA focus on crowdsourcing platform design and user behaviour, China focuses on operational optimisation, such as algorithm development and route planning in dense areas. European countries such as Italy, Germany, Portugal, and the Netherlands also show significant contribution, focusing on how crowdsourcing can be integrated into sustainability, public transport, and urban mobility policies. Africa, South America, and Asia are under-represented.

TABLE 4

TOP 10 COUNTRIES' SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Rank	Country	Country affiliation count
1	China	114
2	Usa	106
3	Italy	58
4	Germany	48

5	Singapore	42
6	United Arab Emirates	42
7	Australia	34
8	Canada	34
9	Portugal	25
10	Netherlands	24

Science mapping

Co-authorship analysis

The country collaboration map visually represents the intensity (colours) and direction (lines) of collaboration between countries in a specific field (Mogire, Kilbourn & Luke, 2025b). The country collaboration map shows that strong collaborations (thicker lines) exist between China and the USA, Canada, and Australia (Figure 2). China and the USA collaborate on integrating advanced technologies into crowdsourcing in last mile delivery. Africa, South America, and parts of Asia are under-represented, offering potential for future collaborations. The highest research output on the topic emanates from the USA, China, and Australia (dark blue colour. In contrast, the emerging/ least research output (light blue colour) emanates from countries like South Africa, Argentina, and Thailand. Most studies in South Africa focus on sustainability, technology enhancement, and integrating public transport systems in the use of crowdsourcing in last mile delivery.

FIGURE 3

COUNTRY COLLABORATIONS MAP ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Country Collaboration Map

Citation analysis

Table 5 shows the top-cited article by Arslan, Agatz, Kroon, and Zuidwijk (2019). In their study, the authors introduced a dynamic model for ad hoc routing in crowd-sourced delivery. This model was relevant because it captured the stochastic and real-time nature of crowd-sourced delivery, which was lacking in prior models. The top-cited publications revealed four main themes: optimisation, environmental sustainability, strategic integration, and acceptance. Most studies focus on optimisation. For instance, Arslan *et al.* (2019) and Wang *et al.* (2016) conducted studies to demonstrate that crowdsourced delivery can reduce delivery costs and improve efficiency. Studies by Devari, Nikolaev, and He (2017), Qi *et al.* (2018), and Gatta *et al.* (2018) showed that a few studies related to the environmental sustainability theme. The studies show that integrating crowdsourcing with public transport or shared mobility reduces emissions and traffic. A study by Castillo *et al.* (2018) focuses on the strategic integration theme, highlighting how crowdsourced delivery can strategically complement conventional delivery by offering flexibility and responsiveness, especially in dynamic urban contexts. Studies by Gatta *et al.* (2018, 2019) and Devari *et al.* (2017), focus on the crowdsourcing acceptance theme, exploring factors influencing user willingness to participate, including age, service features, and social network engagement.

TABLE 5

TOP 10 MOST CITED PUBLICATIONS ON CROWDSOURCING IN LMD

Rank	Authors	Global citations	Title	Summary
1.	Arslan <i>et al.</i> (2019)	321	Crowdsourced delivery—a dynamic pickup and delivery problem with ad hoc drivers	Computational experiments revealed that the use of ad hoc drivers has the potential to make last mile delivery more cost-effective compared to dedicated vehicles.
2.	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2016)	275	Towards enhancing the last mile delivery: An effective crowd-tasking model with scalable solutions.	Comprehensive experiments conducted in Singapore and Beijing datasets formulated a minimum cost flow model that assigns workers to parcels and minimises total delivery costs.
3.	Devari <i>et al.</i> (2017)	234	Crowdsourcing the last mile delivery of online orders by exploiting the social networks of retail store customers.	A survey with 104 participants in the city of Alexandria, Virginia revealed that using friends from social networks for LMD reduces delivery costs and emissions while ensuring reliable and faster service.

4.	Castillo <i>et al.</i> (2018)	177	Crowdsourcing last mile delivery: strategic implications and future research directions	Simulating same-day delivery services from a distribution centre in New York City found that crowdsourced delivery can strategically complement conventional delivery, where flexibility and responsiveness are important for dynamic urban delivery conditions.
5.	Alnaggar <i>et al.</i> (2021)	162	Crowdsourced delivery: A review of platforms and academic literature	A review of platforms and academic literature on crowdsourced delivery found that most studies overlook important operational decisions like driver scheduling, routing, and compensation
6.	Qi <i>et al.</i> (2018)	148	Shared mobility for last mile delivery: Design, operational prescriptions, and environmental impact.	The paper evaluated the impact of shared mobility of passenger cars in LMD, finding that it can create economic benefits by reducing the truck fleet size and exploiting additional operational flexibilities such as avoiding high-demand areas and peak hours.
7.	Gatta <i>et al.</i> (2018)	132	Public transport-based crowdshipping for sustainable city logistics: Assessing economic and environmental impacts.	An extensive stated preference survey and discrete choice modeling in the City of Rome were used to estimate willingness to buy crowdsourcing services and quantify potential demand, finding that older people are less interested.
8.	Gatta <i>et al.</i> (2019)	119	Sustainable urban freight transport adopting public transport-based crowdshipping for B2C deliveries	An extensive stated preference survey in the city of Rome to understand the potential of crowdsourcing as a freight transport strategy. It was found that the location of automated parcel lockers is the most relevant feature for potential crowd shippers.
9.	Frehe, Mehmam & Teuteberg (2017)	114	Understanding and assessing crowd logistics business models—using everyday people for last mile delivery	The paper evaluated the nature and characteristics of crowdsourcing business models in Europe. The study showed that crowdsourcing is a complex issue influenced by economic, social, and technical factors.
10.	Gdowska, Viana & Pedroso (2018)	103	Stochastic last mile delivery with crowdshipping	The paper modelled occasional couriers' probabilistic task acceptance, reducing expected last mile delivery costs by approximately 9%.

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DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results have revealed four key themes used in crowdsourcing in last mile delivery research: optimisation, sustainability, policy integration, and user acceptance. Most studies focus on refining last mile delivery systems through advanced algorithms, particularly in journals like *Transportation Research Part E*. The sustainability theme focuses on integrating public transport to reduce traffic congestion and emissions. Road congestion, air, and noise pollution are linked to increasing parcel volumes from online orders (Mogire, 2022; Mogire et al., 2022; Puram et al., 2022). The most productive authors, like *Pedroso J.* and *Gatta V.* highlight optimisation models and sustainable delivery solutions. The policy integration theme highlights how crowdsourcing can complement existing transportation infrastructures in urban areas. For instance, *Seghezzi et al.* (2021) indicated that a 'hybrid' crowd-sourcing model combines conventional e-commerce delivery vehicles with a group of occasional riders that deliver parcels in small quantities along their route at a fee. However, despite the importance of user acceptance and technological innovations (such as intelligent systems, algorithm, and blockchain), themes remain underexplored. While China and the USA lead research focusing on integrating advanced technologies into crowdsourcing in last mile delivery, there is a notable gap in Africa, South America, and Asian contributions, presenting an opportunity for future exploration. For instance, the implementation of crowdsourcing in Saudi Arabia faces legislative issues, driver availability, trust concerns, and cultural issues (*Alharbi et al.*, 2022).

The future research agenda will address gaps relevant to some key themes identified in the preceding paragraph.

- While the user acceptance theme is recognised as a key theme, it remains underexplored, particularly in Africa, South America, and Asia. Future research should focus on cultural dimensions of user trust, transparency, security, and willingness to participate in crowdsourcing.
- Current research predominantly concentrates on China, the USA, and some European countries. This leaves a significant gap in understanding how infrastructural limitations in underrepresented regions like Africa, South America, and Asia are underexplored. Future research can investigate how infrastructural challenges such as unreliable digital platforms and poor roads affect the feasibility of crowdsourcing in last mile delivery. In addition, future

research can examine how local labour laws, and data privacy regulations affect the uptake of crowdsourcing in last mile delivery.

- While the technological theme is emerging, current research indicates it predominantly concentrates in developed countries like China and the USA. This leaves a gap in Africa, South America, and Asia, as countries in these regions are not represented. Future research can explore the contextual applicability of emerging technologies like intelligent routing systems, blockchain, and dynamic programming in enabling crowdsourcing participation.

THEORETICAL AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study highlights practical and theoretical implications for enhancing crowdsourcing in last mile delivery. Theoretically, the study presents a structured synthesis of four key themes on crowdsourcing in last mile delivery research. These include optimisation, sustainability, policy integration, and user acceptance. These identified themes provide a useful conceptual framework for interpreting current research and guiding future research directions on the topic. In addition, the study highlights regional variations in theoretical development. This highlights the importance of developing models tailored to specific infrastructural, regulatory, and cultural contexts in underrepresented regions.

The four themes identified in this review provide managers and policymakers with a comprehensive framework for designing and implementing context-specific crowdsourced last mile delivery systems that are efficient, environmentally responsible, policy-compliant, and user-centered. Without an integrated approach, crowdsourcing models in last-mile delivery may struggle to address local requirements. This can result in low adoption rates, operational inefficiencies, and reduced long-term sustainability, particularly in underrepresented regions.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This review was limited to a potentially small sample size resulting from the novelty of the topic and the focus on the Scopus database. Future research should include additional databases such as Web of Science and ScienceDirect to include any relevant studies that were overlooked. In addition, this review considered publications in English. To enhance the inclusivity and comprehensiveness of future research, non-English publications should be considered.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this bibliometric review highlights four key themes on existing research on crowdsourcing in last mile delivery: optimisation, sustainability, policy integration, and user acceptance. Despite their relevance, user acceptance and the role of emerging technologies are

still underexplored. Future research should focus on these gaps, especially in underrepresented regions, and examine how new technologies can build user trust and participation. This review provides a useful foundation for guiding research and practical design of more inclusive and efficient crowdsourced last mile delivery systems. However, it is limited by its focus on English-language studies and the Scopus database, which may have excluded relevant global insights.

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